

A Study of Attitude towards Sex-Education as Perceived by Parents & Teachers

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Abstract

The present study aims at the investigation of attitudes of parents and teachers towards sex-education for XI and XII class students. The sample considered 50 teacher and 50 parents of secondary and higher secondary UP Board Students. The teachers and parents were selected on the basis of double stage random sampling. Self constructed questionnaire are used for the study. Sex-education program has also recommended by UNESCO. In India due to the cultural and religious beliefs, generally peoples are not interested to talk about sex-education. So it is necessary to investigate the attitudes of parents and teachers towards sex-education to adolescents.

Introduction

Sex is universally strong biological drive in the life of human beings. It plays an important role in the preservation and building of human society. Much attention has been given to this drive by societies

since the dawn of human civilization. Psychoanalysts have tried to conceive a picture of the inner life of man in terms of sex energy, which is significant source of the action of human beings. The dynamic interplay of inner life of a person, his behavior, expression and experiences are attributed to this source of energy. Sex is supposed to provide certain influences that stress certain factors in human life. So, the normal and abnormal behaviour is related to sexual behaviour. To be natural and normal in this activity, sex-education is needed for human beings.

At all levels of human culture, instruction in matter of sex has been closely bound up with the social moves and the prevailing codes of ethics applied to sex conduct and in development of these codes, the religion has been a dominant factor. The declining influence of religious and social values and the increasing impact of scientific knowledge have brought the problem of sex-education into new focus. Culture in society has to be properly cultivated, so that future generation develops healthy attributes on sex. Parents and teachers have to play the vital role in the life of the adolescents. Generally young adolescents use different strategies to satisfy their curiosities and queries about sex. If adults round them do not provide proper information about sex, adolescents may either draw the wrong conclusions based upon inaccurate knowledge or they will make up their own explanations.

Today, parents have great responsibility in helping child to achieve these behavioural and value changes. For this, they should receive guidance and encouragement from responsible government officials, preferably through formal adult education programme. But the prime responsibility lies with the school system. The educational institutions are better equipped to guide and direct attitude formation, installing skills and competencies than other institution in adolescents about sex-education. Shirur (1998) arrived at a general agreement on the need of adolescents, to be better prepared on sex related health areas to develop readiness for marriage and parenthood. However, there is considerable disagreement and controversy regarding sex-education in human. This controversy has blocked sex-education programmes in schools and colleges for long. Nevertheless due to scientific intervention of United Nation Family Planning Association, India, with the support of UNESCO, a large number of Family Life Education Programs have been implemented in India and other countries.

The responsibility of imparting sex-education must be shared both by parents and the schools together to rescue the young generation from darkness of utter confusions, suspicious taboos and prejudices in the

changing socio economic scenario ruled by on draw porn pictures of sex abuse which instead of growing of positive attitude in their sometimes man their development mass media. Although the nation has taken a big leap on moon and set in the age of ICT revolution, still the country is not yet prepared to welcome the programme of sex-education in schools, because a large proportion of the rural population is ignorant in India. To teach them about sex is extremely difficult. Hence, sex-education is a very vital issue before the country. Therefore there is an urgent need of sex-education through proper organization of educational system. There is much importance of sex-education as a means of developing healthy attitudes among the students.

The scenario is quite changed now today's children are much more intelligent, alert, curious and conscious of the fact that their parents and elders talk some secret behind them. They want to know the secret. If the secret is concealed from them they may take some wrong approach and develop undesirable habits. School teachers are so much traditional and orthodox in their outlook that they do not prefer imparting sex-education as a noble work. Sometimes children satisfy their instincts and get mythical information about sex from sources such as servants, friends, relatives, and T.V. programmes etc., these information may be incorrect and could have spurious effect on them.

Indian society is closed in nature and it follows double standards on the question of sex-education. It generates an utter confusion in the mind of adolescents and sex taboos become a sense of great mysticism in their mind. Adolescent experience a great deal of anxiety emerging out of poor knowledge about their sexual developments, sex and form misconceptions. Sex-education would help students to develop positive attitude towards sex when their queries are satisfied honestly and scientifically. Adolescents have so many myths about their organic development systems, bodily changes, hormonal effects on reproductive system, chronological maturity and its physiological impacts, when they become anxious, stressful and over-pressurized, nobody is their to help, guide and to explain different facts of boy-girl relationship to cope with her / his felt sexual urges.

Attitude

Attitudes are positive or negative feelings that an individual holds about objects, persons or ideas. They are generally regarded as enduring though modifiable by experience and/or persuasion and as

predispositions to action. The needs and the goals of society and the beliefs and attitudes of adults influence the education.

Sex-Education

Sex-education as defined by SIECUS (Sex Information and Education Council of the U.S.) is “a life long process of building a strong foundation for sexual health through acquiring information and forming attitudes, beliefs and values about identity, relationship and intimacy.” The sex-education is defined as education which provides the learner an opportunity to have an access to authentic information and knowledge about the growth, development and related physiological processes of male and female sex organ separately.

Objective of the Study

To study the attitude of parents towards sex-education.

To study the attitude of teachers towards sex-education.

To compare the attitude of teachers at secondary and higher secondary levels.

To findout the relationship between parental education and their attitude towards sex-education.

Hypothesis of the Study

There exists, no significant difference between the attitudes of higher secondary and secondary teachers towards sex-education.

There exists, no significant relationship between the attitudes and education of parents towards sex-education.

Method of Study

Keeping the nature of the problem in the mind Descriptive Survey Method has been used for the collection of the data.

Selection of Sample

All the students of XI and XII classes of Agra district affiliated by U.P. Board of education, the teachers teaching Higher Secondary classes and the parents of the XI and XII class's students constituted the population. In study selection of the school has been based on purposive sampling method on the following grounds.

All schools are affiliated to U.P. Board of Education Allahabad.

Location and distance of the school.

The sample distribution of teachers and parents in Intermediate Colleges in Agra city:

S. No.	Name of School	No. of Teachers		No. of Parents	
		Graduate	Post Graduate	Under Graduate	Graduate
1.	Govt. Inter College, Agra	5	5	5	5
2.	Hubblal Inter College, Agra	5	5	5	5
3.	G.R. Inter College, Agra	5	5	5	5
4.	Chitra. U. M. Vidhya., Agra	5	5	5	5
5.	Rkamal Inter College, Agra	5	5	5	5
TOTAL		25	25	25	25

Construction of Attitude Scale

The researcher has constructed two attitude scales separately for parents and teachers to measure attitude towards sex-education as below:

Parental Attitude Scale towards Sex-education

Teacher's Attitude Scale towards Sex-education

Each Scale consists 30 items which can be rated on Five Point Scale.

Reliability of Tools

Reliability of the "Parental Attitude Scale towards Sex-education" is 0.92

Reliability of the "Teachers Attitude Scale towards Sex-education" is 0.90

Validity of Tools

The introspection reports of the experts and parents were given due consideration and incorporated in the test. On the basis of the above, it can be claimed that parents and teachers attitude scales towards sex-education to adolescents show adequate evidence of content validity.

Statistical Techniques

Descriptive Statistics- Mean, Median & Mode, S.D., Skewness, Kurtosis,

Inferential Statistics- t-Test, Correlation

Graphical Representation of data

Finding of the Study

Findings Related to Objective - 1 - To study the attitude of parents towards Sex-education

The distribution score of parental attitude of overall sample has been found to be negatively skewed and leptokurtic in nature.

Majority of the parents were in favor of providing sex-education to adolescents and they had positive attitude towards sex-education. Mean values of parents on attitude scale was found 108.5 that is high.

Findings Related to Objective - 2- To study the attitude of teachers towards Sex-education

The distribution score of teachers attitude of overall sample has been found to be positively skewed and leptokurtic in nature.

The teachers of XI and XII classes were also in favor of imparting sex-education to adolescents and they have positive attitude towards sex-education. Mean values of teachers on attitude scale was found 107.5 that is high. After analyzing the data statement wise it has been found that majority of the teachers are in favor of sex-education.

Findings Related to Objective - 3- To compare the attitude of teachers at different levels

The attitude of Higher Secondary level teachers (108.9) were found to better is comparison to secondary level teachers. But at both levels of significance this difference was found to be non-significant.

Findings Related to Objective - 4 - To findout the relationship between parental education and their attitude towards Sex-education

It has been found that overall (high qualified and low qualified) correlation between parental attitude and their educational qualification is negligible negative correlation (-0.11).

Testing of Hypotheses

There exists, no significant difference between the attitudes of higher secondary and secondary teachers towards sex-education. This hypothesis has been accepted as a significant difference has not been found in attitude of higher secondary and secondary teachers towards sex-education.

There exists, no significant relationship between the attitudes and education of parents towards sex-education. This hypothesis has been rejected as there is negligible negative correlation between attitude and education qualification of parents.

Conclusions of the Study

The conclusion, which can be drawn on the basis of analysis and interpretation that attitude of parents is higher than teachers towards sex-education. Parent's attitude showing that, they are in favor of sex-education to their adolescents in the school and teacher's attitude showing that, they are in favor of primary sex-education to adolescents start in the family. Attitude of higher secondary teachers and secondary teachers is same towards sex-education to adolescents. Parental education is not affects the attitude of parents towards sex-education to adolescents. Education of parents is not only a single factor which influences the attitude of parents. There are other factors like socio economic status, environment of society and family structure etc. which may influences the attitude of parents towards sex-education.

Limitations of the Study

The study was conducted on only those pupils, parents and teachers, who are in the higher secondary Schools. The study was conducted on small sample of parents and teachers. The study was conduct on schools affiliated to U.P. board in Agra city only. Rural areas were not taken in the present study, there fore scope of the study is limited. Due to shortage of time the student opinion could not be taken.

Educational Implications of the Study

The investigation will help to make the adolescents to realize as important part of the society, to enable them to adjust in the social environment and to appreciate the entire process of growing up. The investigation will help in the construction of the curriculum frame work for sex-education. The preferences in the frame work will be based on the parents and teachers preferences. The investigation will help to adopt a format for developing sex-education. The investigation will help to indentify the existing subjects at different school stages, which will lend themselves to effective integration of the elements of sex-education. The investigation will help in, to search the scope for handling sex-education through classroom teaching and school based activities. The findings of investigation will help teachers to develop insight into parents-child relationship at adolescent level.

Suggestions

Adolescence is the period of storm and stress. They form the largest part of our society and will form the future parenthood. It is the responsibility of parents, teachers and society as a whole to give them right knowledge regarding sex.

1. For Parents

This study is of great importance for parents. Parents should try to understand the needs, Queries and confusion of the adolescents. It is advisable for the parents to have good rapport with their children. They should give honest answer to their queries. It is not only the responsibility of teachers but also of parents.

2. For teachers

The teacher is in a position to facilitate the enrichment of the positive traits and alleviate the effect of negative ones, myths and misconceptions through aids. They should understand their duties and expectations of parents. They should not have the apprehension that teaching sex-education will tarnish their image. The teachers can use different methods as:

Suggestion box

Essay writing competition

Case study method

Painting competition

Group discussion

3. For Administrators & Policy Makers

This study will also be helpful for administration of schools such as in making provision for health environment in school for teaching and learning. They can provide various facilities, which would help in increasing teachers' effectiveness in the field of sex-education. Administration should bring awareness among teachers about the responsibility towards students, society and nations as a whole. The study is equally helpful for policy makers, as it will help framing the points to be included in teacher

training packages. This facilitates the teachers to have an idea of the content and many determine his methodology.

4. For Guidance Worker

Guidance plays an important role in improving the people's attitude and behavior. Proper guidance programme must be arranged for parents and adolescents. This should be organized on scientific basis by which awareness towards sex may be developed in the public. Guidance for the every day simple problems can be undertaken by teachers, parents and others concerned, provided they have the attitude, knowledge and patience to undertake it.

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